

ON THE DISTRIBUTION OF $\phi(\sigma(N))$

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Abstract

Let $\phi(n)$ be the Euler totient function and $\sigma(n)$ denote the sum of divisors of n . In this note, we obtain explicit upper bounds on the number of positive integers $n \leq x$ such that $\phi(\sigma(n)) > cn$ for any $c > 0$. This is a refinement of a result of Alaoglu and Erdős.

1. Introduction

For any positive integer n , let $\phi(n)$ be the Euler-totient function given by

$$\phi(n) = n \prod_{p|n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right),$$

where p runs over distinct primes dividing n . Let $\sigma(n)$ be the sum of divisors of n , which is given by

$$\sigma(n) = \sum_{d|n} d = n \prod_{p^k || n} \left(\frac{1 - p^{k+1}}{1 - p}\right).$$

Here the notation $p^k || n$ means that p^k is the largest power of p dividing n . In 1944, L. Alaoglu and P. Erdős introduced the study of compositions of such arithmetic functions. In particular, they showed that for any real number $c > 0$,

$$\#\{n \leq x : \phi(\sigma(n)) \geq cn\} = o(x) \quad \text{and} \quad \#\{n \leq x : \sigma(\phi(n)) \leq cn\} = o(x).$$

In [3], F. Luca and C. Pomerance obtained finer results on the distribution of $\sigma(\phi(n))$. The objective of this paper is to study the distribution of $\phi(\sigma(n))$.

Denote by \log_k the k -fold iterated logarithm $\log \log \cdots \log$ (k -times). We show the following result.

Theorem 1. *For every $c > 0$,*

$$\#\{n \leq x : \phi(\sigma(n)) \geq cn\} \leq \frac{\pi^2 x}{6c \log_4 x} + O\left(\frac{x \log_3 x}{(\log x)^{\frac{1}{\log_3 x}} \log_4 x}\right),$$

where the implied constant only depends on c .

This implies that except for $O\left(\frac{x}{\log \log \log \log x}\right)$ integers less than x , $\phi(\sigma(n)) < cn$ for any $c > 0$. It is possible to replace the constant c above by a slowly decaying function. For a non-decreasing real function f , define

$$P_f(x) := \left\{n \leq x : \phi(\sigma(n)) \geq \frac{n}{f(n)}\right\}.$$

Then, we prove the following.

Theorem 2. *Suppose $f : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is a non-decreasing function satisfying*

$$f(x) = o(\log_4 x).$$

Then,

$$|P_f(x)| = O\left(\frac{xf(x)}{\log_4 x} + \frac{x \log_3 x}{(\log x)^{\frac{1}{\log_3 x}} \log_4 x}\right) = o(x)$$

as $x \rightarrow \infty$. In other words, for almost all positive integers n , $\phi(\sigma(n)) < \frac{n}{f(n)}$.

Choosing $f(x) = \log_5 x$ in Theorem 2, we obtain the following corollary, which is an improvement of the result of Alaoglu and Erdős [2].

Corollary 1. *Except for $O\left(\frac{x \log_5 x}{\log_4 x}\right)$ positive integers $n \leq x$,*

$$\phi(\sigma(n)) \leq \frac{n}{\log_5 n}.$$

2. Preliminaries

A necessary component of our proof is to estimate the number of positive integers not greater than x which do not have certain prime factors. Such an estimate requires an application of Brun's sieve. For our purpose, we invoke the following result by P. Pollack and C. Pomerance [4, Lemma 3].

Lemma 1. *Let P be a set of primes and for $x > 1$, let*

$$A(x) = \sum_{\substack{p \leq x \\ p \in P}} \frac{1}{p}.$$

Then uniformly for all choices of P , the proportion of $n \leq x$ free of prime factors from P is $O(e^{-A(x)})$.

We also recall the famous Siegel-Walfisz theorem (see [5, Corollary 11.21]).

Lemma 2 (Siegel-Walfisz). *For $(a, q) = 1$, let $\pi(x; q, a)$ denote the number of primes $p \leq x$ such that $p \equiv a \pmod{q}$. Let $A > 0$ be given. If $q \leq (\log x)^A$, then*

$$\pi(x; q, a) = \frac{\text{li}(x)}{\phi(q)} + O\left(x \exp(-c\sqrt{\log x})\right),$$

where the implied constant only depends on A and $\text{li}(x) := \int_2^x \frac{1}{\log t} dt$.

For any prime p , define

$$S_p(x) := \#\{n \leq x : p \nmid \sigma(n)\}.$$

The main ingredient in the proof of Theorem 1, which is also interesting in its own right, is an upper bound for $S_p(x)$.

Lemma 3. *For any prime p and $x \geq e^p$*

$$S_p(x) = O\left(x \left(\frac{\log \log x}{\log x}\right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}}\right),$$

where the implied constant is absolute.

Proof. Note that for any prime $q \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$, all n such that $q \parallel n$ satisfy $p \mid \sigma(n)$. Thus, to obtain an upper bound for $S_p(x)$, it suffices to estimate the number of $n \leq x$ such that either $q \nmid n$ or $q^2 \mid n$ for a subset of primes $q \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$. By Lemma 2, for $x > e^p$, we have

$$\pi(x; p, -1) = \frac{x}{(p-1)\log x} + O\left(\frac{x}{(\log x)^2}\right),$$

where the implied constant is absolute. Now suppose x is sufficiently large such that $\log x > e^p$. Applying partial summation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{\log x < q < x \\ q \equiv -1 \pmod{p}}} \frac{1}{q} &= \frac{\pi(x; p, -1)}{x} - \frac{\pi(\log x; p, -1)}{\log x} + \int_{\log x}^x \frac{\pi(t; p, -1)}{t^2} dt \\ &= \frac{1}{p-1} \int_{\log x}^x \frac{1}{t \log t} dt + O\left(\frac{1}{\log_2 x}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{p-1} (\log_2 x - \log_3 x) + O\left(\frac{1}{\log_2 x}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Now, applying Lemma 1 with P being the set of primes $q \equiv -1 \pmod p$ and $\log x < q < x$, we obtain that the number of $n \leq x$ free of prime factors from P is

$$O\left(x\left(\frac{\log_2 x}{\log x}\right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}}\right).$$

Since

$$\#\{n \leq x : q^2 \mid n \text{ for prime } q \equiv -1 \pmod p \text{ and } \log x < q < x\} \ll x \sum_{\log x < q < x} \frac{1}{q^2} \ll \frac{x}{\log x},$$

we have the lemma. □

3. Proof of Theorems 1 and 2

Proof of Theorem 1. Note that

$$\phi(\sigma(n)) = \sigma(n) \prod_{p \mid \sigma(n)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right)$$

Denote by $P(y) := \prod_{p \leq y} p$, the product of all primes $\leq y$. If $P(y) \mid \sigma(n)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\sigma(n)) &= \sigma(n) \prod_{p \mid \sigma(n)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ &\leq \sigma(n) \prod_{p \leq y} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) < \frac{\sigma(n)}{\log y}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality follows from Mertens's theorem (see [5, Theorem 2.7 (e)]), namely

$$\prod_{p \leq y} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) < \frac{1}{\log y}.$$

Thus, for any $c > 0$, the inequality $\phi(\sigma(n)) < cn$ holds if $P(y) \mid \sigma(n)$, $\sigma(n) < \delta n$, and $(\log y)^{-1} \leq c/\delta$. We know that (see [1, Theorem 3.4])

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \sigma(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12}x^2 + O(x \log x).$$

Using partial summation, we get

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\sigma(n)}{n} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}x + O(\log^2 x).$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \#\{n \leq x : \sigma(n) \geq \delta n\} &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ \sigma(n) \geq \delta n}} 1 \leq \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\sigma(n)}{n} \\ &= \frac{\pi^2}{6\delta} x + O\left(\frac{\log^2 x}{\delta}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\#\{n \leq x : \sigma(n) < \delta n\} \geq x \left(1 - \frac{\pi^2}{6\delta}\right) + O\left(\frac{\log^2 x}{\delta}\right). \tag{1}$$

From Lemma 3, we also have

$$\begin{aligned} \#\{n \leq x : P(y) \nmid \sigma(n)\} &\leq \sum_{p \leq y} |S_p(x)| \\ &= O\left(x \left(\frac{\log_2 x}{\log x}\right)^{\frac{1}{y}} \frac{y}{\log y}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\#\{n \leq x : P(y) \mid \sigma(n)\} \geq x \left(1 - O\left(\left(\frac{\log_2 x}{\log x}\right)^{\frac{1}{y}} \frac{y}{\log y}\right)\right). \tag{2}$$

Choosing

$$y = \log_3 x \quad \text{and} \quad \delta = c \log_4 x$$

in (1) and (2), we obtain

$$\#\{n \leq x : \phi(\sigma(n)) < cn\} \geq x - \frac{\pi^2 x}{6c \log_4 x} + O\left(\frac{x \log_3 x}{(\log x)^{\frac{1}{\log_3 x}} \log_4 x}\right).$$

Hence,

$$\#\{n \leq x : \phi(\sigma(n)) \geq cn\} \leq \frac{\pi^2 x}{6c \log_4 x} + O\left(\frac{x \log_3 x}{(\log x)^{\frac{1}{\log_3 x}} \log_4 x}\right),$$

which proves Theorem 1. □

Proof of Theorem 2. We use the exact same method as in the proof of Theorem 1, with the choices

$$y = \log_3 x \quad \text{and} \quad \delta = \frac{\log_4 x}{f(x)}$$

in (1) and (2). This gives

$$\#\left\{n \leq x : \phi(\sigma(n)) < \frac{n}{f(n)}\right\} \geq x - O\left(\frac{xf(x)}{\log_4 x} + \frac{x \log_3 x}{(\log x)^{\frac{1}{\log_3 x}} \log_4 x}\right).$$

This proves Theorem 2. □

4. Concluding Remarks

The study of composition of multiplicative arithmetic functions seems to be a difficult theme in general. This has also received scant attention, except for a very few instances such as [2] and [4]. For example, it is not clear if $\phi(\sigma(n))$ has a normal order. It would be desirable to develop a unified theory for such functions and perhaps construct families of multiplicative functions whose compositions have a finer distribution.

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